

STORY JOKES AND ITS ROLE IN READING SKILL

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***Annotation** The aim of the study is to check and define reading skills achievement through humor and joke stories of students provided in the theoretical part and used in the lessons in terms of the progress of the language of the learners and their general satisfaction with the lessons. The main objective of the research is to provide insights into the role of story jokes in the improvement of reading skills.*

***Key words** –story, joke, humor, competence, novelty, classification, socio-cultural competence, language competence, speech competence, compensatory competence, structure, language knowledge, reading skill.*

INTRODUCTION

The process of reading has a huge impact on the formation of personality. With the help of reading in English, students enrich their active and passive vocabulary of words, form grammatical skills and there is a study of the culture of this language. One of the main problems of learning to read is the problem of selecting texts and clearly organizing work with them. Improvement of old traditional forms of education and search for new means, forms, methods, adequate to the development goals of participants in the educational process, is the actual problem of modern education, in the aspect of which the study was carried out. The practical significance of the research lies in the development and application in practice during pedagogical practice for learners in Tashkent region of a set of exercises and different reading strategies like story jokes aimed at teaching reading skills to learners in their EFL lessons.

II BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Currently, there are a number of studies proving the usefulness of using humor in education, including foreign language. The positive influence of humor on the educational process boils down to the following:

1. Humor and jokes contribute to the creation of a comfortable environment in the classroom, the appearance of a sense of spontaneity. Immediacy is a pedagogical concept meaning the degree to which a teacher establishes close personal relationships with students, as opposed to maintaining distance and restraint. The described sense of immediacy ultimately leads to the fact that students have a positive attitude towards the subject and the teacher, which increases motivation and the quality of learning the material.

2. The material accompanied by joke is remembered better than information submitted exclusively in a serious manner. This statement suggests that humor can be considered as one of the techniques of mnemonics. When learning a foreign language, all of the above is useful, since memory is of fundamental importance in this process. However, when using humor for better memorization of the material, it is necessary to remember that humor should have a close connection with the content of the course. In addition, it is advisable to use humor a little and to illustrate the most important concepts, and not secondary material.

3. Currently, in many textbooks, including foreign language textbooks, you can find funny drawings and other humorous materials illustrating the information in the text, which, according to a number of studies, help students to better assimilate the material and increase motivation for the subject being studied.

Despite all the positive results described above from the use of joke in education, there are a number of caveats. Firstly, aggressive forms of humor, such as sarcasm, ridicule and offensive humor and have no place in the classroom. Secondly, the potential risk is the use of humor with young children, as they may misinterpret it, due to the inability to understand what it is based on. According to

M. Rod, (2009) a distorted humorous image in young children, due to its novelty, can be easily remembered and hardly pushed out of memory.

According to G.G. Pocheptsov, (1982) the study of humor fully contributes to the realization of all required competencies:

Speech competence: The British actively use humor, both in personal and business communication, including with foreigners. Familiarity with various variants of humor gives students the opportunity to adequately respond to its manifestation in a conversation and continue it, perhaps in a humorous way, as well as to recognize humorous forms different from Uzbek language in the written or heard text.

Language competence: English humor is a lingua–humor that allows you to take a different look at the possibilities of the language, better understand its features, and much more productively assimilate such phenomena that are not present in your native language.

Socio-cultural competence: Humor is a translator of values, ideals, views, lifestyle of the people. Its study allows you to reveal the features of another culture and get to know the features of your own better.

Compensatory competence: In intercultural communication, all kinds of difficult situations are possible, and humor helps to overcome them, this is one of its main social functions.

In addition, English humor is considered refined, elegant and intellectual, so familiarity with it can lead to the development of students' healthy aesthetic understanding of the comic.

III METHODOLOGY

By experimenting and comparing the data obtained, the analysis process was based on quantitative research methods. The following methods were essentially used according to the subject classes, such as the different approaches in teaching reading skill, gap-filling exercises, multiple choice tasks, interactive methods of teaching reading skill by using story jokes, accessible evaluation applications. They

used in the study process are the incorporation of approaches to improving the competency of learners in reading skills and their use in education.

The researcher used various approaches to collect data on accomplishments. The researcher asked the chosen students questions and took notes of their responses. The questions were asked in order to find out the attitude of students in their lessons towards using different story jokes. With the help of story jokes instruction, one of the groups should be developed reading skills, while the other group should be usually taught in a traditional way of improving reading abilities.

A. Object

The object of the study is to use of story jokes instruction in teaching reading skills and to identify its impact, affecting the language capacity of learners as a current trend in English Language Teaching. The results of pre and post-tests, questionnaires on the application of language teaching use during the classes, are the data from this report. The data sources in this analysis are case, descriptive and documentary.

B. Subject

Lesson plans, some reading texts, questionnaires and quizzes were given for the subjects of these courses. Students practiced reading, vocabulary, translation and grammar aspects in every lesson in order to use them to develop their reading abilities in class. To identify the efficacy of story jokes in developing reading skills in EFL classes, the researcher wanted to compare the results of the participants of one group with other group students who were taught with the help of reading strategies instruction and at the end of the analysis, the researcher intended to compare the results of the two groups on learned topics.

C. Materials and equipment

Questionnaires, lesson plans, schedule, various materials from course books were the study materials. Student's book, Work Book and Dictionary were used during the research process. In this report, various types of required lesson equipment such

as: board, projector, laptop, loudspeakers, markers, stickers, paper, activity cards, handouts, pictures and others were also used within the materials. Each of these devices was used effectively: boards were used for brainstorming, reading criteria, rules and formulas, clustering and evaluating an object in a wide range of its usage; stickers visually in front of the view of learners; activity cards helped to coordinate different leveled and targeted steps of the lesson, while handouts and photographs for individual compositional tasks; the projector was used to play video materials as well as power point presentations, the laptop proved its necessity by sounding lexeme pronunciation, and was used in various repairs, the computer room was used by the installed quiz makers for the entire target group to practice improvement of reading abilities through the lessons.

IV DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The researcher's qualitative approach is used in observation sheets. It is designed to observe the entire lessons in detail. In addition, needs assessment is structured to consider the needs, desires and attitudes of learners towards the teaching of group work. Pre and post-tests consist of lessons in reading skills. At the start of the teaching process, the pre-test is taken and the post-test is taken at the end of the learning process. Experimental courses were used to perform the present research. First, before beginning to work with them and having pre and post-tests, the researcher wanted to observe some lessons from experimental courses in order to compare the findings at the end of the study.

Observations The researcher prepares sheets for observation. The investigator followed lessons from experimental and control courses for about two weeks in conjunction with the measures and directions of the observation sheets. The actions of teachers and the techniques they used were examined and the mistakes were also noticeable when studying the lessons of others. In addition, learners were also relaxed with the observer at the lesson through the days, making it easier to perform

the coming lessons. Since the students must have learned and adapted to the new teacher already.

Questionnaires Two separate questionnaires were used in this study. Questionnaires were made by researcher. The questionnaire was administered with teachers, firstly, and then with the students. The questionnaire demonstrates the learners and teachers' personal views and desires. This is important for the research as well. Since the instructor should pay attention to the needs and desires of the learners while preparing the lesson.

Questionnaire for teachers The first questionnaire was for teachers to collect required ideas, teaching reading thoughts, teaching through story jokes instruction methods and traditional ways of teaching. The questionnaire included 10 teachers. The researcher gave the questionnaires to the English teachers at the very education she/ he was in. The researcher obtained the answers and gathered from them the overall information.

Questionnaire for students The next one was aimed at getting information about their needs and difficulties in English classes from the learners. Since most of them had some trouble interpreting the context of the questions, this process took more time. The researcher helped them understand the context and choose the answer, taking this into account.

The researcher was able to obtain a lot of valuable information for the report. Gathered ideas and thoughts were taken into account in the analysis after reviewing the learners' questionnaire documents.

Pre-test It was created to check and assess the learners' current knowledge of reading skills as well as their context. This test enables the researcher to choose appropriate tasks for the following lessons. To begin with, appropriate tasks for the B1 level were chosen for the exam, as their level was expected to be B1 according to their teachers. Before the students took the test, the researcher outlined what they could do with these tests. Students were assessed based on the following criteria:

Table1. The criteria for assessing reading skills of the learners in the Pre-test stage

5 (excellent)	4 (good)	3 (satisfactory)	2 (bad)	1 (too bad)	0 (not done)
Only 3-4 incorrect answers	No more than 5-8 mistakes	Over 9-13 incorrect answers	Approximately 14-18 mistakes	19-25 incorrect answers	Over 26-30 mistakes

Post-test After practicing in two months with two group students' reading skills it was the time to check their developed final knowledge. As teaching students' reading skills in two ways, final post-tests were prepared and conducted. Experimental and Control groups submitted the post-test examination with doing reading activities through story jokes instruction based ones.

It's crucial to compare post-test results to pre-test results, and it's simple and straightforward to see the progression after comparing percentage scores.

Table2. The criteria for assessing reading skills of the learners in the Post-test stage

5 (excellent)	4 (good)	3 (satisfactory)	2 (bad)	1 (too bad)	0 (not done)
Only 3-4 incorrect answers	No more than 5-8 mistakes	Over 9-13 incorrect answers	Approximately 14-18 mistakes	19-25 incorrect answers	Over 26-30 mistakes

V RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study confirmed that English teachers believe their concerns, questions and English teaching problems in EFL contexts are not adequately discussed. The study's participants discussed the drawbacks of teaching English as a foreign language. As a result, more emphasis should be placed on research that focuses on the unique characteristics of English learning and teaching in EFL settings.

Table3. The Pre and Post-test scores and Percentage of change for each group

Tests	Pre-test	Post-test	Difference between the scores	Percentage
	Mean	Mean		
Experimental group	18.1	24	5.9	3.25
Control group	19	22.7	3.7	1.94

Finally, the testing cycle was ended with positive results of the experimental and control groups. The experimental group's result was higher, with the help of teaching their reading skills through story jokes, in comparison with control group, but also their attitudes also shifted towards improving to positive side. According to the table, experimental group's pre-test mean score was 18.1 and the post-test mean score was 24 and the difference between the scores was 5.9. The researcher achieved his goal with improving experimental group's percentage to 3.25% with utilizing their reading skills lessons. When it comes to control group, the group's pre-test mean score was 19 which had been higher than experimental group and post-test mean score was 22.7. The difference between the pre and post-test scores was 3.7 and the percentage of the group was raised to 1.94% because the researcher used traditional way of teaching reading with classroom textbooks, handouts and others.

Here are several suggestions to make this study more useful for teachers and researchers in order to enhance reading achievement using story jokes methods in the future. First and foremost, the teacher must carefully prepare the lessons before implementing them in the classroom. It is critical to consider the correct procedures/steps for each technique by consulting expert theory. Second, since the lesson plan guides the teacher in implementing activities in the classroom, it is best if the practices in the lesson plan are synchronized with the implementation in the classroom. Third, by using story jokes approach to teach English, the teacher should accept and demand the use of target language in any classroom activity so that students are encouraged to use English as their primary mode of communication. Finally, given the limitations of this study, further research is needed to perform experimental studies on the best story jokes based practice for improving reading skills of learners.

VI. CONCLUSION

This qualification paper developed a methodology for developing the skill of reading in a foreign language on the basis of story jokes instruction methods. A number of restrictions, as seen in the analysis, have made story jokes difficult to implement incorporated into English classrooms. One of the key factors is that due to their heavy workload, teachers do not have the time or resources to create appropriate materials and events and teachers' heavy workload should be reduced. As a result, their working conditions should be changed.

A reform of the current examination system is also needed. According to the results of this research paper, educational spheres place much too much emphasis on grammar-based tests and as a result, English teaching practices are influenced by the skills assessed in these exams, which are primarily grammar and vocabulary skills. Other language skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing should be prioritized. More research on how to measure learners' reading skills in a teaching reading setting should be done for this reason. It may be worth considering that

large-scale summative tests should not be used as the sole criteria for selecting and placing students for future education. Formative exams, on the other hand, should be integrated into English education. Students' reading abilities can be better reflected in selection and placement instruments from this viewpoint. Similarly, such a reform will improve both teachers' and learners' incentive to teach and learn reading through story jokes.

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